

PROSPECTIVE SOLUTIONS FOR THE PROPER ORGANIZATION OF TRAFFIC IN CITIES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CITY OF URGENCH)

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Annotation. *This article provides suggestions and recommendations for the integrated development of road transport systems in the cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of the study of design solutions for the proper organization of traffic in cities (on the example of Urgench).*

Keywords. *cities, transport infrastructure, road network, density, transport hubs, access roads to the city, overpasses, parking lots.*

Introduction. In recent years, the interest of the whole world in the historical cities, historical and cultural heritage of the Republic, as well as its ecological location is growing. is an important feature of it. The overall development of the economy, the quality of life of all segments of the population depends on the effective functioning of this system. At the same time, as a result of the rapid increase in traffic on urban roads, the capacity of the streets will decrease, the speed of vehicles will decrease, traffic jams will occur at most single-level intersections, Such situations lead to an increase in fuel consumption of vehicles, loss of passenger time, as well as aggravation of a number of economic, social, environmental, sanitary and hygienic conditions, such as increased emissions and traffic noise.

Formation of an effective system of urban transport management on the basis of a comprehensive approach to the design, construction and operation of the city road network, in order to improve the system of their financing, to create a full-fledged customer service that will allow to improve the quality of design and construction work in this area Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 9, 2019, No. PP-4545 "On measures to further improve the management system of the road sector" According to the resolution, it is necessary to eliminate all the shortcomings on the city streets using innovative technologies. In particular, along with the removal of water from highways, the

elimination of traffic jams, the complex development of tourist routes in historic cities and the proper organization of traffic is one of the pressing issues.

Materials and methods used According to the results of scientific research conducted in recent years in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the comfortable, economical and safe movement of vehicles in urban roads, as well In the future, based on advanced foreign experience, it is necessary to study the current state of urban street networks in the future to conduct research to increase the capacity of urban streets and ensure safe traffic and control of access roads to the city without traffic lights. According to the Khorezm regional department of highways of the Committee for Motor Roads of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of bridges on public roads in Khorezm region is 875, of which 6 are overpasses. The total number of bridges in the region is 1,592.

The total length of public roads in Khorezm region is 2210 km, of which:

- 1) A380 - The length of the road of international importance is 113 km.
- 2) The length of the road of state importance is 706 km.
- 3) The length of the local road is 1391 km

The length of public roads in Urgench is 35 km. The length of the city road is 268.8 km. The length of local roads is 243 km.

One of the main indicators of the level of development of transport infrastructure in the global urban planning experience is the density (d) of the city road network. This figure is characterized by the ratio of the length of the street-road network to the urban area.

$$\delta_{yM} = L/S$$

here:

δ_{yM} – density of the total street network of the city, km / km²;

L – length of general street-road network, km;

S – total area of the city, km².

Results. An integrated (mixed) scheme of organization of the street-road network is common in urban planning practice. This is especially true for large and ancient cities that have traversed important paths in the evolution of urban planning.

Socio-economic and demographic development of the republic is characterized by an increase in the urban population and sustainable development of urban settlements. The location of the urban population determines the essence of the overall structure and parameters of the transport system. In urban planning, the density of the urban road network depends on another important factor, which is the coefficient of nonlinearity (K_n) of the urban street network. The magnitude of this coefficient depends on the layout of the city street network.

According to the State Statistics Committee, the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan as of January 1, 2022 is 35271276 people. Of these, 1924,167 people, or 5.55% of the population of the republic are residents of Khorezm region. The population of Urgench is 146,749 people, which is 8% of the total population of Khorezm region. The volume of freight traffic in Khorezm region, especially in Khiva, is growing steadily, as a result, the number of vehicles in the city is constantly increasing. The increase in the number of cars makes the city streets unable to accommodate them. These cases, which occur on city streets, are related to the speed of traffic. As the intensity of city streets, refers to the total number of vehicles passing in a given section of time on a given section of the street.

$$K_n = \frac{W_{month}}{W_{year}}$$

here: W_{month} - monthly movement intensity;

W_{year} – annual traffic intensity;

From the main highways leading to Urgench: 4r 156 Urgench-Khanka, 4r 157 Urgench-Yangiariq, 4r 158 Urgench-Khiva, 4r 159 Urgench-Shovot, 4r 160 Urgench-Gurlan, 4r 161 Urgench-Cholish, a large flow enters the city through highways. In this study, the traffic volume was analyzed at the section of these 6 main highways connecting with the city of Urgench.

Figure 1. Traffic congestion on the road to Urgench

The change in traffic intensity during the day is mainly due to two values: 7⁰⁰ — 9⁰⁰ in the morning and 17⁰⁰ — 19⁰⁰ in the evening. At this time, the townspeople go to study, work and return. The main traffic on the road during the day will be observed at this time. The main flight during the day is 12 -14 hours (during). As can be seen from the diagram, In the 6 largest transport hubs of the city of Urgench, the highest flow of vehicles is observed in the morning and evening. An important infrastructural component of the goal of creating appropriate conditions for the sustainable development of the regions is the transport infrastructure, and one of its key elements is the passenger transport system. Minimizing the number of entrances and exits of vehicles in urban areas in the design practice specific to the Far East and the use of overpasses at the entrances to the city makes it possible for vehicles to move safely provided that.

A balanced transport system is singled out as the highest form of passenger transport system development. In this case, the main transport hubs of the cities are analyzed, provides for the planning of overpasses at transport hubs.

Urgench has 6 main transport node (TN), a large stream enters the city through these 6 TNs. Today, As the number of domestic tourists visiting cities increases, causing a number of transportation problems in the city.

In addition, The share of combined trips in the Republic of Uzbekistan is growing: road transport system (RTS) of reach the nearest station by private

Figure 3. Planning at the entrance to the city of Urgench and within the city.

Conclusion. The increase in the number of light vehicles in our cities is a good indicator, of course. But they are, in fact, in the local settlements where the population lives becoming one of the most pressing issues today to move safely. That is why our cities are at the crossroads and to drivers of vehicles through the planning of special overpasses in the city area and to prevent the accumulation of toxic odors from pedestrians and vehicles and turning urban areas into eco-friendly areas is driven by safe traffic lights that hurt great conveniences we consider the design of the conductors to be promising rojas.

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